

THE PERMEABILITY OF GLASS FIBER MAT AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE FILLING TIME OF RTM PROCESS

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SUMMARY: Resin transfer molding (RTM) is an attractive process of fiber reinforced polymer composite manufacturing. The permeability of the preform or flow mobility is an important parameter which indicates all the detailed microscopic interactions between the fluid and the fiber preform architecture. It influences the flow of resin in the mold. This work took random distributed continuous glass fiber mat as an example which is widely used in RTM process, studied the relationship between preform permeability and fiber volume fraction in the mold. The influence of the preform architecture on the permeability and mold filling time as well as resin impregnation was analyzed. The relationship between permeability and mold filling time was investigated.

KEYWORDS: resin transfer molding, preform permeability measurement, polymer processing

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) is an attractive process for polymer composites manufacturing. In this process, a fiber preform of reinforcing material is placed in the mold. The mold is then closed, and the precured resin is injected into the mold. The resin impregnates the fiber preform and fills the mold where it cures to create a composite part.

The mold filling pattern for flow of a fluid through the fiber preform depends on a number of parameters. The part geometry, the location of the injection gates, injection pressures or flow rates are perhaps the most obvious ones. Another parameter which will influence the mold filling pattern is the structure of the fiber preform. Fiber preforms with different geometries or fiber arrangements will offer different resistance to the flow[1].

Most liquid composite molding (LCM) such as resin transfer molding (RTM) and structural reaction injection molding (SRIM) mold filling models apply Darcy's law in which the flow characteristic of the fabric reinforcement is represented by the permeability[2]. For one-dimensional flow of Newtonian fluids, the Darcy's law is given by

$$u = -\frac{k}{\mu} \frac{dp}{dx} \quad (1)$$

in which u is the volume averaged velocity in the porous medium, k is the permeability of the porous medium, μ is the viscosity of the fluid and $\frac{dp}{dx}$ is the pressure drop.

Although the permeability of simple fibrous structures such as unidirectional fibers with ideal packing can be predicted[3], most of commercially used fabric reinforcements do not have simple structure and their permeability has to be measured experimentally[4].

The random distributed continuous glass fiber mat is a kind of reinforcement which is widely used in RTM process. The measurement of its permeability will give a great help to the composites industry. In this work, the permeability of different volumes of random distributed continuous glass fiber mat reinforcement in the mold was measured. In order to compare the permeability between random distributed continuous glass fiber mat and other different structure reinforcement, the permeability of certain volumes of bi-directional woven fabric in the mold was measured too. The relationship between the permeability of glass fiber mat and the mold filling time was investigated, and the influence of the preform architecture on the permeability and mold filling time as well as resin impregnation was analyzed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The measurement liquid is DOP oil (diphenyl-octyl-phthalate). Its viscosity was a function of temperature and ranged from 0.038 to 0.050 Pa · s (38 to 50 cp) at room temperature. A vinyl-ester resin (MFE-2, Hua Chang Polymer Corporation, Shanghai) was used for analyzing the difference of the permeability and the mold filling time between random distributed continuous glass fiber mat and bi-directional woven fabric. The viscosity of the resin was 0.45 to 0.55 Pa · s(25°C, spinning viscosity meter) at room temperature.

The two types of glass fiber mats were random distributed continuous glass fiber mat of 450g/m² surface density (Nanjing Institute of Glass Fibers, Nanjing) and a bi-directional woven fabric of 283g/m² surface density (Yao Hua Glass Fiber factory, Shanghai).

Equipment

In this work, the one-dimensional flow experiments were conducted. A rectangular mold cavity was created by placing a 4 mm thick spacer between two platens of metal. The cavity dimension was 250×110×4 mm. The spacer was drilled at both ends to create an end gate and a vent directly across from the gate. The fiber mats were positioned in the mold cavity 10 mm from the inlet to leave the injection point uncovered. Thus, it eliminates radial flow and create a line source for axial flow. The liquid was forced through the molds from a pressure-pot system. The fluid flow was measured at a mold exit with volumetric measurements. The pressure was measured at the inlet with a pressure transducer.

Permeability Measurement

It is well known that many of the difficulties in the experimental permeability measurement of composite reinforcements lie in the cutting and handling procedures required to place the materials in the experimental molds [5]. Therefore, the fiber reinforcements are prepared and

placed in the mold very carefully in order to minimize the edge effect and achieve constantly reproducible results.

Assuming Darcy's law is valid during the mold filling, then the flow Q and pressure p data collected during the experiments were analyzed to get the permeability values. The surficial velocity u was computed by dividing the flow by the total cross sectional area of the fluid flow path A and the superficial velocity was then plotted as a function of the pressure gradient. According to the Darcy's law, the slop of a linear least squares fit of the data is k/η . The value used for the fiber volume fraction was the total preform weight divided by the approximate density of glass ($\approx 2.5\text{g/cm}^3$).

In the actual permeability measurement, because the flow leakage along the side of the fabric reinforcement, the effective permeability must be larger than the real values. In fact, the edge effect is unavoidable in the one-dimensional flow in the actual production. Therefore, here the effective permeability were measured.

If we want to account for the edge effect, the proposed method estimating the edge flow effect in Ref. 6 can be used. The method in Ref. 6 can be summarized as following. In the unidirectional flow measurement, in addition to the central region with bulk permeability k_c , the regions near the side walls are assumed to be with a different permeability k_e , as shown in Fig.1. Using two fiber samples with different widths, we can derive the following relationship,

$$\frac{Q_1 \mu L}{h p_1} = W_1 k_1 = 2W_e (k_e - k_c) + W_1 k_c \quad (2a)$$

$$\frac{Q_2 \mu L}{h p_2} = W_2 k_2 = 2W_e (k_e - k_c) = W_2 k_c \quad (2b)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 represent two different sample widths, and k_1 and k_2 are the effective permeabilities.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the edge flow effect in unidirectional flow

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In-plane Permeability of Random Continuous Fiber Mat

For random distributed continuous glass fiber mat, the measured effective permeability and calculated permeability using the empirical model suggested by Raymond Gauvin et al. in Ref.7 are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 2.

Table 1: The measured and calculated permeability data for random distributed continuous glass fiber mat

Layers of fiber mat n	Fiber volume fraction v_f	Measured effective permeability $k / \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$	Calculated permeability $k / \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$
4	0.180	2.83	2.92
5	0.225	1.76	1.88
6	0.270	1.23	1.42
7	0.315	0.97	1.15
8	0.360	0.85	0.96

Fig. 2: The relationship between permeability k and fiber volume fraction v_f

From Table 1 and Fig. 2, it can be seen that the fiber volume fraction in the mold has the important effects on the preform effective permeability. For in-plane permeability of random continuous glass fiber mat, the relationship can be roughly expressed as

$$k = Av_f^3 + Bv_f^2 + Cv_f + D \quad (3)$$

here $A \approx -457.25$

$B \approx 437.04$

$C \approx -143.19$

$D \approx 17.196$

$$v_f = \frac{n\xi}{H\rho_g 10^{-3}}$$

where n is the number of layers of fiber mat, ξ the surface density of the reinforcement (g/m^2), H the laminate thickness (m) and ρ_g the glass mass density (kg/m^3).

The experimental data of effective permeability is close to the calculated permeability using the empirical model for the permeability prediction of continuous strand reinforcing mats by Raymond Gauvin et al. in Ref. 7:

$$k = a + b \exp(c\phi) \quad \text{for } 0.65 \leq \phi \leq 0.90 \quad (4)$$

where ϕ is the porosity. Taking a , b , c from the Table 2 of Ref. 7 (U101 from Vetrotex, they are 736.6, 4.46×10^{-3} , 15.95 respectively).

Filling time vs. Effective permeability

Fig. 3: The relationship between mold filling time t and permeability k

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between mold filling time t and measured effective permeability k . It indicates, at a constant flow rate (here 10ml/s). The higher the permeability, the shorter the mold filling time is needed.

In the experiment, some considerations must be taken into account. The volume of the fiber reinforcement can not be too high and too low. If the volume fraction of the fiber is too high, it is very difficult to close the mold. The excessive clamping forces must be applied, which will cause the deformation of the mold. The higher fiber fraction and lower permeability in the mold need higher mold filling pressure which may cause the deformation of the mold or make the reinforcement deform. It will affect the distribution of the preform in the mold. In molding practice, it decreases the size accuracy of the molded parts and the deformed reinforcement will affect the properties of the designed article.

If the volume fraction of the fiber reinforcement is too low, The preform may slip and form wrinkles or fold locally, when the fluid passes through the fiber preform. A small change in flow rate or filling pressure can be sensed during mold filling.

The effects of the preform architecture

Fig. 4 shows the comparison of the mold filling time for random distributed continuous glass fiber mat with bi-directional woven fabric.

In order to analyze the effect of the architecture of the fabric reinforcement on its permeability, the bi-directional woven fabric was chosen as an example to compare with the

random distributed continuous glass fiber mat. We measured the permeability of bi-directional woven fabric. When the $v_f = 0.36$, its effective permeability is $0.42 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$. This value is almost half the permeability of random distributed continuous fiber mat.

At the same filling pressure (0.1 MPa), the mold filling time is shown in Fig. 4 (150 seconds for random distributed continuous glass fiber mat, 341 seconds for bi-directional woven fabric). The filling time of bi-directional woven fabric is more than two times than that of random distributed continuous fiber mat.

Fig. 4: The comparison of the filling time for random continuous glass fiber mat with bi-directional woven fabric

After the resin cured, we cut some samples from the molded parts to analyze the fiber impregnation. It was found that the impregnation of the random continuous glass fiber mat is much better than that of bi-directional woven fabric. Especially at the filament-filament crossover points of bi-directional woven fabric, the impregnation of the fabric is poor. The reason of poor impregnation was analyzed as following. In bi-directional woven fabrics system, we can treat it as two kinds of regions. The first kind of region is associated with regions bordered by adjacent filaments of each weave direction. The second kind of region is the filament-filament crossover points. At a crossover point, filaments of one weave direction intersect filaments of another. The permeability in these regions is much lower than the first kind of regions. They offer the largest resistance to the forced penetration of a fluid. From the macroflow point of view, the fluid passed through those regions. But from the microflow point of view, the fluid did not penetrate the fiber filament. The poor fiber impregnation will affect the interface bound strength of fiber and resin and the mechanical properties of the molded composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The fiber volume fraction in liquid composites molding (LCM) influences the preform permeability. The relationship between permeability k and fiber volume fraction v_f for random distributed continuous fiber mat can be expressed as a polynomial equation. In one-dimensional flow permeability measurement, the edge effect is inevitable, but it can be minimized by careful sample preparations to get the reproducible results. The architecture of the fiber reinforcement has great influence on the preform permeability. For the preform of same fiber volume fraction, but different architecture, their permeability can be much

different. In the actual LCM production, the permeability measurement and calculation should be carried out for different architecture and different fiber volume fractions. The mold filling time depends on the reinforcement permeability at some extent. The random continuous fiber mat has much higher permeability than bi-directional woven fabric even the fiber volume fraction is the same. The molded composite using random continuous fiber mat as reinforcement has better fiber impregnation than that using bi-directional woven fabrics.

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